

Organizational Structure Of Students' Independent Work In Credit-Module Environment

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Abstract: In the article, the issues of organizing independent education of students in the higher education system are studied in a general way, their types, the necessary competences in independent education are covered in detail

Key words and phrases: education, competence, information environment, individual, independent education, organization, skills, competence.

Introduction

In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, "increasing the share of independent education hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurship skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, making the educational process practical orientation to the formation of skills, in this regard, the wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on international educational standards into the educational process.

In educational and scientific research institutions of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries, scientific research works are being carried out on improving the independent work of the participants of the educational process, forming the personal-professional, creative potential and integrative thinking of students, clarifying the psychological properties of online teaching, and expanding the pedagogical possibilities of interdisciplinary integration. At the same time, special attention is paid to the use of modern didactic tools in the development of students' independent work competences, improvement of vocationally oriented educational content, wide use of multimedia, information and communications, and improvement of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of creative abilities in students.

The goal of informatization of education is global acceleration of intellectual activity due to the use of information and telecommunication technologies. Within the framework of solving these issues, studies and researches aimed at developing the pedagogical, methodical and technological bases of combining technologies and information tools into one system have been conducted, and the information-educational environment as such a system is the most optimal.

The information-educational environment is a tool that ensures the transfer and rapid exchange

of educational information. On the basis of this environment, an opportunity is created for students to understand each other, to respect the opinion of others, to express their opinion freely, and to learn to solve problems together. As a result, the unified field of education is penetrated.

In order to effectively organize the information-educational environment, the following must be taken into account: multiple, systematic, one-time or long-term observation of natural, physical, social and other phenomena, data collection from different regions; comparative study of events, evidence, trends in different places, making decisions and developing proposals; comparative study of the effectiveness of ways to solve each problem or issue (alternative or different methods), taking into account the differences between the cultural, ethnic, geographical conditions of network participants; comparative analysis of social and cultural views, taking into account specific cultural, traditional and other characteristics; development of a creative idea (practical, creative, scientific and other) under the condition of joint research of a specific problem; conducting competitions on studying and solving educational problems and focusing on problem situations that arise in relation to cultural and educational traditions in other areas.

There are encyclopedic views of our thinkers regarding the implementation of active creative non-standard learning by students in the information-based educational environment, training in mental activity, organizational methods, tools, as well as technology of engagement by the student, enthusiasm for work, motivation, inclination, interest, and emotional aspiration. they are expressed as follows.

The use of information technologies opens up new opportunities for organizing students' independent work. The organization of independent work in the information-educational environment is becoming a new, individual learning by students; open educational resources are emerging as content; technical means of education in global network technology, means of communication - various social services of the Internet; the priority organizational form of education has a positive effect on the independent activity of students; independent learning, networking and co-creation are becoming leading learning methods.

The analysis of the essence of the concept of "independent activity of students" presented in the scientific literature revealed two main points of view: the activity carried out independently by the student without the direct participation of the professor-teacher, but under his guidance; is a form of educational process that ensures the achievement of educational goals. The shift of education to mixed forms of education and the transfer of the educational process to the information-educational environment is an effective form of the educational process and a means of implementing a new educational paradigm, which increases attention to the independent activity of students.

In order to effectively organize independent educational activities of students and professors in the environment of higher education, professors and students are required to have the following

necessary competencies:

1. 1. Information-technological competence;
2. 2. Research competence;
3. 3. Communicative competence;
4. 4. Competence to manage and develop one's own activities.

A competent approach in the information environment does not mean that knowledge and skills are acquired separately, but that they are mastered collectively. Informatics and information technologies play an important role in this process. Because, thanks to the rapid development of information and communication technologies, computers are entering both professional and everyday life of a person, and computer skills are becoming a vital necessity for any professional. The study of information technology has a practical and applied nature. It is necessary to form the point of view of students towards the computer as a means of their activity, which helps to solve various issues. In this regard, it is necessary to choose the optimal means and methods of solving a specific task with different software. As a proof of our opinion, an electronic program was created on the subject of "Educational Work Methodology", and the program is directly based on the issues of organizing classes for students based on information and communication technologies (Appendix 4).

Therefore, it is necessary to form qualities such as the ability to solve problems correctly, plan activities to solve them, analyze the results, make a critical assessment, and understand that the goal has been achieved.

Carrying out independent studies in an information-educational environment is necessary not only for information technology knowledge, but also as an important means of self-development, self-improvement and self-awareness of a person. That's why students should realize and understand the inadequacy of their previously acquired knowledge and skills, form a learning task together with the professor, and be able to self-evaluate. The task of the professor-teacher is to create favorable conditions for the student's independent education and self-development, to encourage him to work independently in solving the assigned task. In this process, the competence to manage and develop one's own activities plays an important role.

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